

**Analysis of metallurgical iron slag from the archaeological excavations
in Kyiv, Volodymyrska Street, 20 – 22
(head of the excavations – I.I. Movchan, 1999)**

Metallurgical slag K – 99, Вл. 20, Р. 1., Сл. 3. refers to the slag of a large metallurgical complex located in the "City of Yaroslav". Its size is evidenced by the large amount of slag that was found nearby in the ravine, where the waste was dumped. One of these slags is the one we have investigated.

The metallurgical slag taken for the study had a size of ~ 14 x 10 x 5 cm, a shape close to an oval, curved at the bottom, slightly concave at the top. Thus, the slag repeated the shape of the slag collector located in the lower part of the furnace.

The slag has an uneven surface on the outside. It is covered with a crust up to 0.5 cm thick and has a complex mineral composition: iron hydroxides, clay minerals, carbonates (calcite). Inside, the slag is black, hard, and porous.

To study the slag, petrographic, X-ray structural (XRD), spectral and chemical analyses were used. To conduct petrographic analysis, thin sections and polished sections were made from different areas of the slag. Petrographic studies were performed by V.I. Ganotsky (National Mining University). XRD analysis was performed at the department of metal physics of the Dnipropetrovsk National University by V.O. Golovko (diffractogram recording) and T.I. Anishchenko (calculation of interplanar distances), spectral and chemical analyses were performed in the Central laboratory of the SE "Yuzhnekrgeologiya", spectral analysis was performed by V.S. Solodovnyk and S.O. Yermieva, chemical analysis was performed by O.P. Deineka.

The main primary mineral phases of the slag are wüstite and olivine (fayalite), which are present in approximately equal proportions or with a slight predominance of fayalite. In addition, the slag contains 2% cementite and 5-10% charcoal inclusions. Secondary minerals are goethite and hydrogoethite, which make up 10-15% of its volume.

Wüstite (FeO) forms subspherical grains (globules) with a size of 0.015 - 0.025 mm, usually collected in chain and dendrite-like aggregates, which are in close intergrowths with fayalite and together with it form a solid solution decomposition structure (photos 1,2,3,4). In transmitted light, wüstite is opaque (black), in reflected light (in polished sections) - light gray with a brownish tint, low reflective ability ($R \approx 15\%$), internal reflexes are absent, hardness is medium (on the Mohs scale = <5) - it is scratched with a steel needle. Weakly magnetic. In the XRD analysis of the slag, the values of interplanar distances obtained correspond to the reference values for wüstite.

Fayalite (Fe₂SiO₄). In thin sections, it is transparent, slightly yellowish with sharply visible relief and shagreening, which corresponds to refractive indices within $n = 1.85 - 1.95$. Cleavage is imperfect, extinction relative to cleavage is direct, birefringence is high ($\Delta = 0.040 - 0.045$), the angle of the optical axes is negative, about 45° ($-2V \approx 45^\circ$), dispersion of the optical axes is strong $r > v$. It forms hexagonal, columnar (photo 2) or tabular (photo 1) crystals. The length of the hexagonal crystals is 6 - 8 mm with a thickness of 0.2 mm, columnar - 1.5 - 2 mm with the same thickness, tabular grains have a size of 0.2 - 0.8 mm.

Olivine is typically saturated with a large number of wüstite inclusions and forms a typical pyrogenic solid solution decomposition microstructure (photos 3, 4). The X-ray data of fayalite fully corresponds to the reference data.

Cementite (Fe₃C). Occurs in small quantities in the form of rounded grains (globules) ~ 0.03 mm in size, which form elongated aggregates and several grains (photo 4). In specular light, yellowish white with high reflectivity ($R \approx 60\%$). Hardness is high (cannot scratched by a steel needle).

Charcoal. Forms fragments of subrectangular shape, 5-10 mm in size. Opaque in sections, retains signs of relict wood structure. In some places it is replaced by goethite (photo 7).

Goethite (FeO • OH). Forms microgeodes in slag pores and inclusions in charcoal (photos 5, 7). Translucent red brown in thin sections, gray in specular light, anisotropic, $R \approx 15\%$, red brown internal reflexes, hardness above average.

Hydrogoethite ($\text{FeO} \cdot \text{OH} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Forms crusts on pore walls (photos 3, 4) and in some places partially replaces fayalite. Yellow and yellow brown in transmitted light, gray in reflected light with $R \approx 17\%$. Hardness is medium (can be scratched with a steel needle), internal reflexes are yellow brown.

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the slag reveals a number of reflections characteristic of cementite and goethite.

The results of spectral analysis for trace impurities showed the following results ($\%^{-3}$): Ba – 50; Be – 0.1; p – 100; Cr – 0.7; Ga – 0.1; Ni – 1; Zn – 1.5; Zr – 5; Ti – 20; Cu – 3; Mn – 100. The high content of manganese and phosphorus is noteworthy. This may be due to the characteristics of the local soil or man-made factors.

Chemical analysis of the slag gave the following results: (%): SiO_2 – 16.8; Al_2O_3 – 2.2; Fe_2O_3 – 30.1; FeO – 39.2; TiO_2 – 0.2; P_2O_5 – 1.4; MnO – 0.18; CaO – 4.0; MgO – 0.45; K_2O – 0.57; NaO – 4.3; H_2O – 0.21; втрачено при горінні – 0.92; Σ – 100.32; Fe (general) – 51.4.

Thus, we have a typical raw blast furnace slag with a rich iron content (more than half). The high calcium content (4%) is noteworthy, which indicates the use of fluxes. It should be noted that when performing the chemical analysis, a transverse plate from the middle of the slag was used, which reflected all its zones, including the outer crust, which, however, could affect the results of the chemical analysis. But, in general, studies have shown that the slag is the result of the reaction of the iron compound with molten ore impurities, and then prolonged oxidation of this conglomerate.

The results of the chemical analysis of the slag correspond to the average indicators of chemical analyses of slags from other metallurgical centers of Kyivan Rus, which indicates the uniformity of technologies throughout the territory of the Rus State.

Photo 1. Slag microstructure. Black – wüstite, light yellow – fayalite, white – pores. Transmitted light, nicols (-), 70^x

Photo 2. Microstructure of the slag: columnar crystals of fayalite (yellow) separated by aggregates of wüstite (black) and containing a large number of inclusions of the latter. Transmitted light, nicols (-), 23^x

Photo. 3. Dendrite-like aggregates of wüstite (black) in fayalite. White areas of irregular or oval shape are pores, on the walls of which there are hydrogoethite crusts (yellow and yellowish brown).

Transmitted light, nicols (-), 100^x

Photo 4. Microstructure of the slag in a polished section. Bright white vertically elongated aggregate in the center is cementite, grayish white oval-shaped grains on the left, collected in non-intersecting chains (solid solution decomposition structure) are wüstite, light gray ribbon on the right is hydrogoethite crust on the pore wall (dark gray), gray field is fayalite.

Reflected light, nicols (-), 70^x

Photo 5. Goethite microgeode of metalloid texture (brownish red with black), formed at the site of a pore in the slag during its weathering. Black, microporous substance at the top is charcoal, yellowish at the bottom is fayalite.

Transmitted light, nickels (-), 70^x.

Photo 6. Hydrogoethite crusts on the walls of pores in the slag (keels of the rim). Bright white areas in the slag mass are wustite, light gray is fayalite, gray is pores.

Reflected light, nicols (-), 70^x

Photo 7. Fragment of charcoal (black) with relict cellular-vascular structure. Red-brown areas in the charcoal are goethite, yellow areas are fayalite, black inclusions in fayalite are wüstite. Transmitted light, nicols (-), 70^x.